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ABSTRACT

The ARIES WP15 program was focused on the development of superconducting thin films (TF) for superconducting radio-frequency (SRF) cavities. This final WP15 report is highlighting the main results achieved within the four-year programme. The TF quality is defined by their substrate, thus Task 15.2 was focused on the copper sample preparation and surface polishing. The procedures initially developed on small samples were applied to a larger area of Quadrupole Resonator (QPR) samples. Task 15.3 on thin film deposition and characterisation is at the core of the WP15 programme, the expertise available at partner institutes allows to progress from Nb films to the successful development of superconducting thin films different from Nb, such as NbN, Nb₃Sn and NbTiN thin films. Evaluation of thin films in Task 15.4 included an evaluation of superconductivity properties with DC magnetisation methods on small samples and the RF testing on QPR samples. Many new results have been obtained over the last year and are reported below. Four technologies, which have not been used in the past for the R&D related to the SRF cavities, have been explored. Two of them were found to be practical for the SRF applications: a laser treatment of Nb films and a magnetic field penetration measurements.

WP15 team achieved all its goals, the Milestones and Deliverable have been successfully completed.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

This report summarizes the main achievements of WP15 programme:

Copper sample preparation and surface polishing have been developed on small samples and applied to the Quadrupole Resonator (QPR) samples. The programme on development of superconducting non-Nb thin films such as NbN, Nb₃Sn and NbTiN thin film has been completed. This programme included deposition, characterisation, evaluation of superconducting properties and RF testing. These results enabled the WP team to progress with SIS multilayer structures using NbN and Nb₃Sn with AlN as an insulator.

Four technologies, which have not been used in the past for the R&D related to the SRF cavities, have been explored. Two of them were found to be practical for the SRF applications: a laser treatment of Nb films and a magnetic field penetration measurements.

WP15 achieved all its goals, the Milestones and Deliverable have been successfully completed. The knowledge and experience obtained by WP partners in copper substrate preparation and deposition of non-Nb TF materials with higher T_c are enabling progressing to the next stage: developing a real cavity prototype coated with non-Nb superconducting and SIS thin films. The potential benefit of this should be increasing of Q_0 and E characteristics, a possibility of operation for SRF cavities at 4 K instead of 1.8 K leading to reducing the initial and operation costs the RF systems.

1. Introduction

Over four years a WP15 team followed the scope and the roadmap of the WP15 programme which had been set before the starting date for the ARIES project. All activities of WP15 are connected, cross-correlated and integrated in one international project. Deliverable Report D15.1 summarised the WP15 progress with evaluation of copper substrate cleaning and polishing process. Two procedures for surface preparation of Cu for Nb coating were chosen for the following WP15 activities base on various types of characterisation of copper surface and Nb film deposited on it [1]. The following activities were focused on developing the thin films (TF) based on superconducting (SC) materials different from pure Nb. The choice of materials was discussed in detail in Deliverable Reports D15.1 and D15.2 [1,2] and based on literature survey [3-7]. The development and evaluation of Systems 1 (Nb₃Sn) and System 2 (NbN) has been reported, describing the details of deposition, surface analysis, structural analysis, and DC superconductivity evaluation. Deliverable Report D15.3 [8] is related to the development of System 3 (NbTiN) and SIS (superconductor-insulator-superconductor) multilayer coatings [9-10].

This final report on the WP15 programme is highlighting the main results achieved within four years. A considerable fraction of the work summarized here has been presented at various journals or conferences (see [11-20]) or going to be reported in near future at IPAC'2021 and SRF2021 conferences.

Another significant part of the WP15 activities is focused on evaluation of SC TF at the conditions similar to ones in accelerator radio-frequency (RF) resonators. The Quadrupole Resonator (QPR) facility developed in earlier H2020 projects is employed for this activity [21]. Some results have been reported in D15.3 [8] and in Ref. [22]. This report describes new QPR results obtained at the RF conditions at HZB Berlin.

2. Polishing of copper substrate before SC thin film coating on samples and an impact on the Nb film SC properties

Substrate preparation in superconducting accelerating cavities is fundamental in order to achieve the best RF performances. The influence of surface preparation is deeply studied for bulk Nb cavities and it is responsible for the main performance advancement. Although different studies were performed in past [22-24], the preparation of Cu substrate used for the Nb thin film accelerating cavities has not been developed as for bulk Nb, and nowadays the scientific community agrees in considering the Cu surface preparation one of the main issues for the Nb thin film accelerating cavities. The first goal of ARIES WP15 has been the study of the influence of Cu surface polishing on the SRF performances of Nb coatings. A comparison of 4 different polishing processes for Cu (Tumbling, EP, SUBU, EP+SUBU) has been done through the evaluation of the SC and morphological properties of Nb thin

films coated on Cu planar samples, polished with different procedures. Effects of laser annealing on Nb thin films have also been studied (see Section 5.2).

2.1 POLISHING TECHNIQUES EMPLOYED IN THIS PROJECT

Operatively the effect of copper polishing has been studied through the evaluation of the morphological and superconductive properties of Nb thin film coated on the polished copper planar samples. The cleaning and polishing procedures were carried out at CERN and INFN LNL. At CERN 25 copper planar samples were treated with SUBU solution as reference, at INFN another 25 samples were divided in 4 different batches, one for each treatment investigated: SUBU solution, EP, SUBU+EP and Tumbling. On 15 out of the 50 treated copper planar samples, a Nb coating was done. The deposition processes were carried out at STFC, University of Siegen and INFN, 5 samples each, using the same procedure and similar parameters. Samples treated in the same cleaning and polishing batch were coated in more than one laboratory, in order to minimize the role of the deposition facility on the SC film properties. Laser treatment was also tested as post-treatment on 5 Nb coated samples, at Riga Technical University (RTU). The sample workflow is reported in Table 1. For QPR samples a dedicated polishing protocol has been developed.

2.1.1 At CERN

CERN has been in charge of the production of 50 samples with a size of 53mm x 53 mm obtained from a single copper OFE sheet by mechanical cutting. 25 samples (C1-C25) have been chemically polished using SUBU5 solution removing ~40 μm of material. More details in ARIES D15.1 [1]. The other 25 samples (L1-L25) have been sent to INFN LNL.

Table 1: Samples workflow scheme of surface polishing evaluation task. For each sample are reported all the processes done and the treatment facility.

SAMPLE PROCESS #	SAMPLE NAME														
	C1	C7	C10	L1	L19	L20	L10	L13	L16	L23	L18	L21	L9	L4	L8
Sample production	CERN	CERN	CERN												
Sample labeling	CERN	CERN	CERN												
Sample shipping				to LNL	to LNL	to LNL	to LNL	to LNL	to LNL	to LNL	to LNL	to LNL	to LNL	to LNL	to LNL
SUBU Polishing Process	CERN	CERN	CERN	LNL	LNL	LNL									
EP Polishing Process							LNL	LNL	LNL						
EP+SUBU Polishing Process										LNL	LNL	LNL			
Tumbling Cleaning procedure													LNL	LNL	LNL
Surface characterisation				LNL	LNL	LNL									
Sample shipping	to U.Siegen	to STFC	to LNL	to U.Siegen	to STFC										
Nb coating	U.Siegen	STFC	LNL												
Sample cutting	U.Siegen	STFC	LNL												
Surface characterisation	U.Siegen	STFC	LNL												
Sample shipping	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU	to RTU
SC magnetization characterisation	RTU	RTU	RTU												
Sample shipping			to RTU												
Laser post-treatment			RTU												

2.1.2 At INFN

Samples L1-L25 have been divided in 4 different batches, one for each treatment investigated: SUBU solution, EP, SUBU+EP and tumbling. For all the processes, except tumbling, 40 µm of material has been removed in order to have comparable results. A surface characterization was done after each treatment and consists of roughness evaluation, SEM and ESD analysis. More details in ARIES D15.1 [1].

2.1.3 At RTU

An addition to standard mechanical, chemical and electrochemical processes, laser polishing of copper has been explored in this project, see Section 5.1.

2.1.4 Main observations

Five different characterizations were done at INFN to evaluate the copper surface after the polishing: optical inspection, reflectivity, SEM and EDS. From a simple optical inspection significant differences are visible (see Fig.2.1). The SUBU samples present a mirror-like surface, EP samples present a mirror-like surface with a diagonal texture due to the oxygen evolution during the EP process and the absence of a bath agitation. In the EP+SUBU samples, SUBU process reduced the texture, but did not remove it completely. Tumbling samples present a shiny surface (but not mirror-like as SUBU and EP samples) with small scratches visible only examining the sample from a certain angle.

Figure 2.1: Copper surface after the polishing treatments

Reflectivity characterization presents similar values for all the treatments (64-66%), except Tumbling one, that presents a lower reflectivity (52%), confirming the visual inspection.

The SEM characterization (Fig. 2.2) shows a very smooth surface on the EP sample. SUBU produces pitting on the surface, visible also in the EP+SUBU sample. On the other hand, SEM micrographs confirm the presence of a large amount of scratches and defects on the surface of tumbling sample. EDS characterization was also performed on each sample and no visible contaminations appear.

Figure 2.2: SEM micrographs of the four treatments evaluated.

2.2 THIN FILM DEPOSITION

2.2.1 Nb film deposition at INFN, STFC and University of Siegen

The substrates were prepared by INFN and CERN and were delivered to coating partners STFC, University of Siegen and INFN. Subsequently, Nb thin films were deposited on copper samples from each procedure using direct current magnetron sputtering (DCMS). Although the deposition configuration is different from one centre to another, the deposition parameters were set to be comparable. The procedure and the applied deposition parameters in all three deposition facilities are reported in D15.1 [1].

2.2.2 Nb film laser treatment at RTU

The five samples coated at INFN, as well as a few samples coated at STFC, have been sent for laser post-coating-treatment to RTU. Laser irradiation of Nb/Cu samples has been performed in an Ar

atmosphere by a focused laser beam that scans over the sample surface. Details of laser treatment are described in Section 5.2.

2.2.3 Main observations

Here are reported only the characterizations done on Siegen series of coating as representative of all the samples coated. The full characterization analysis is present on Deliverable Report D15.1 [1].

Figure 2.3: SEM micrographs of the coated surface and roughness measured by AFM.

Figure 2.3 shows SEM investigations of all five samples. It becomes obvious that on the SUBU samples two different grain structures can be observed, that are: areas with smaller grain size and lower surface mean roughness (Ra), and areas with larger grain size and, therefore, higher surface roughness. The findings correlate with the SEM investigations of the uncoated substrate: it is shown that the SUBU pre-treatment leads to anisotropic etching of the different grain orientations on the polycrystalline Cu substrate. This, in turn, leads to different growth mechanisms of the deposited film. Another phenomenon of the SUBU treatment revealed by the SEM investigations is pitting, which leads to areas with very high roughness values and high deviation of these values. The EP, by contrast, shows less deviation of Ra which also correlates with the SEM investigation. The SUBU treatments present the lowest and the highest roughness values according with SEM investigations that reveal a different etching depending on different grain orientations.

2.3 MAGNETISATION MEASUREMENTS OF Nb/Cu SAMPLES

2.3.1 Magnetisation measurements at IEE

Flux penetration into the superconducting Nb films deposited on Cu substrate has been investigated by means of magnetisation measurements. Using a commercial Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) set-up, virgin DC magnetization curves and magnetization loops were measured on small measurement samples of approximately 2 mm × 2 mm. These were cut with the help of a laboratory cut-off machine using a SiC cut-off disc. The main characteristic determined from the magnetization curves was the first flux entry field B_{en} , determined as the applied field at which the magnetic flux starts entering the sample's volume. Details regarding the measurement procedure and the B_{en} determination can be found in the Deliverable Report D15.3 [8].

Figure 2.4: Overview of the first flux entry field (H_{en}), determined in (a) parallel and (b) perpendicular applied magnetic field, for the Nb films on Cu substrates polished with different techniques.

Comparison of B_{en} values of the Nb/Cu films is shown in Fig. 2.4.

Considering the DCMS deposited samples, the highest values were measured in the series deposited at STFC Daresbury. These samples had the Nb film thickness of $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ (due to a deposition rate calibration issue), while for the series of samples deposited at INFN Legnaro and Siegen University the typical Nb thickness was $3 \mu\text{m}$. Very encouragingly, the best performing films deposited employing the HiPIMS method repeatedly show B_{en} values comparable to or slightly exceeding the best DCMS films, although the nominal Nb film thickness was $3 \mu\text{m}$ as well. The different series of HiPIMS samples were part of an optimisation study where the deposition parameters were varied in a certain range. Therefore, more pronounced performance variations are observed between samples within the series.

2.3.2 Magnetic field penetration measurements at STFC

A field penetration facility has been designed and built at STFC, which applies a local parallel DC field from one side of the sample to the other. The details of the experimental facility are described in Section 5.2. The initial tests were focussed on the effects of substrate polishing on Nb deposition.

The field of full flux penetration (B_{fp}) for various Nb/Cu samples obtained with this facility are shown in Fig. 2.5 as a function of sample temperature.

Figure 2.5: Overview of the field of full flux penetration (B_{fp}) for the Nb films on Cu.

The main result is that the highest B_{fp} obtained were on substrates polished with SUBU5 or EP, while the lowest correspond to EP+SUBU5. Thus, these B_{fp} measurements confirm the earlier B_{en} results obtained with VSM.

2.4 QPR POLISHING

The polishing protocol for QPR has been developed from the results obtained in D15.1 and two possible polishing methods have been chosen: electropolishing (EP) and chemical polishing (SUBU5). The protocol has been adapted to re-treat the QPR after the coating and RF test to produce a fresh copper substrate on the top ready for a new coating (see updated workflow Fig. 2.6). In particular, mechanical polishing has been avoided and 3 more surface treatments have been added: indium removal, Nb chemical stripping and persulfate etching.

Figure 2.6: QPR workflow. For each process is reported the treatment facility. Indium removal and persulfate etching processes are included in “Nb chemical stripping” step.

Indium removal

After the RF test, some indium residuals remain on the flange (see Fig. 2.7). Indium etching is done with chloridic acid diluted to 10-16%. Depending on the adhesion of Indium, the process could take from a few minutes to a maximum of a few tens of minutes.

Figure 2.7: Indium residuals on the QPR flange.

Nb chemical stripping

A selective removal of Nb film avoiding copper substrate etching is mandatory before proceeding with the Cu polishing process. It was decided to use an industrial solution of chemical stripping, called “Strip AID”, that is based on the HF:HBF₄=2,5:2,5 v.r. and addition of the organic surfactants

in the quantity of 100 g/l. The solution allows removal of the Nb, with a negligible attack of copper, so that, after a removal of the niobium film, the copper substrate surface can be still reflective. However, with prolonged exposure, the surface of the copper may become matte. It was found that 3-4 hours are necessary to remove 4 μm of Nb film. As a side effect, with time, the solution can be oversaturated with copper ions so that a chemical spontaneous deposition of copper can take place onto the Nb surface. It was also found that a fast persulfate etching could be a useful treatment prior to Cu polishing, to highlight possible areas with Nb not totally removed.

Persulfate etching and EP

It can be useful to do a persulfate etching (5-10 min. long) of the Cu surface before the final EP, to ensure that the surface is perfectly stripped by Nb film. Persulfate etch preferentially the grain boundaries and can be used also to emphasize substrate grain structure. With this procedure it has been noted a non-uniform copper grain size dimension along the QPR top surface (see Fig. 2.8).

A fast EP (10 min.) after persulfate etching is done to remove copper oxide and polish the Cu surface. After high pressure rinsing (HPR) using water, the QPR is ready for a new coating process.

Figure 2.8: On the left QPR after persulfate etching. On the right a non-uniform viscous layer is visible during the EP of a surface with small residual of Nb film. The Nb protects the copper substrate from dissolution and must be removed by repeating the chemical stripping process.

2.5 SUMMARY ON POLISHING

Five surface treatments techniques: SUBU, EP, EP+SUBU, Tumbling and Laser Polishing, prepared in three different institutions on an identical planar substrate have been investigated. Based on the morphological characterization, the main conclusion is that the best procedure is EP, as it produces a pitting free surface with a uniform grain structure. It seems SUBU provides the surface with the lowest roughness, but with a non-uniform grain structure and surface pitting that is better to avoid in SRF applications. Superconducting properties of Nb films show a slight difference between

deposition facilities rather than different surface preparation. However, both B_{fp} and B_{en} measurements report the lowest values for the EP+SUBU5 treatment in all the 3 series of samples. Laser polishing of the Nb film results in an increase of both B_{en} and B_{fp} , but the polishing effect still has the same pattern: the highest values are still for SUBU5 and EP and the lowest for SUBU5+EP. Based on these results a surface preparation protocol has been developed for QPR samples based on EP.

3. Developing of non-Nb SC thin film coating

The consortium continued to develop coatings with thin film of superconducting materials other than Nb, such as Nb₃Sn (System 1), NbN (System 2), NbTiN (System 3) as well as SIS multilayer structures. The deposition performed on the samples prepared in Year 1: flat OFHC samples with dimensions 53 mm × 53 mm × 2 mm. The samples are polished with either SUBU or EP, two polishing procedures defined as most promising in Year 1 [1]. The Report D15.2 [2] reported on Systems 1 (Nb₃Sn) and System 2 (NbN) describing the details of deposition, surface analysis, structural analysis, and DC superconductivity evaluation. The Report D15.3 [8] is related to the development of System 3 (NbTiN) and SIS (superconductor-insulator-superconductor) [9-10]. Below the main achievement on SC TF are summarised.

3.1 DEPOSITION AT STFC

The next step was to determine the best deposition parameters for synthesising higher T_c superconducting materials such as NbN, Nb₃Sn, NbTiN, V₃Si as an alternative superconductor thin film to be used in either single layer or SIS formation. It should be noted, that unlike Nb all other alternative SRF material can only be used in SRF cavity form in thin film structure.

3.1.1 System 2: Nb₃Sn thin films

The Nb₃Sn films were deposited using an alloy target. The successful superconducting phase was synthesised at deposition temperature of 650 °C. The film composition was determined by the Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) and the Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS), which showed stoichiometric composition of the superconducting phase, and the X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis also showed a very good match with other reported literature results. The critical temperature was found to be 17.5 K on copper and 17.75 K on sapphire, which is very close to theoretical value of 18 K. The magnetisation loop determined by VSM showed the first penetration field $B_{en} = 90$ mT for copper and $B_{en} = 140$ mT on sapphire. An example of this series of work is shown in Fig. 3.1, which represents the cross-section SEM of a perfect layer of Nb₃Sn deposited on copper as single (a) and double layer (c) with their corresponding DC magnetizing loops (Fig. 3.1 (b) and (d), respectively). The B_{c2} for both cases was determined to be above 16 T, which is the maximum limit of the VSM.

Figure 3.1: (a) X-section SEM of Nb₃Sn deposited on copper, (b) corresponding magnetisation loop for a single layer, (c) X-section SEM of Nb₃Sn with a Nb underlayer as double structure on copper, (d) corresponding magnetisation loop for a double layer.

3.1.2 System 3: NbTiN thin films

Thin films of NbTiN as part of another alternative layer were investigated. They were synthesised using both an alloy target of NbTi and a dual target configuration of Ti and Nb target. The latter allowed a host of combinations to be examined as with alloy target the only composition which was explored was stoichiometric Nb_{0.25}Ti_{0.25}N_{0.5}. Thin films were again deposited in single layer as shown in Fig. 3.2 and multilayer SIS structures were deposited. The critical temperature was found to be 17 K both on copper and on sapphire, which is very close to theoretical value of 18 K. The magnetisation loop determined by VSM showed the first penetration field $B_{en} = 57$ mT for copper

Figure 3.2. (a) X-section SEM of NbTiN deposited on sapphire with a dual target.

and $B_{en} = 25$ mT on sapphire. The B_{c2} for both cases was determined to be above 16 T, which is the maximum limit of the VSM.

3.1.3 SIS structures

Having identified the optimum deposition parameters for depositing high T_c superconductor of Nb_3Sn and $NbTiN$, a series of multilayer SIS structures were deposited with a substrate temperature of 650°C . When Nb_3Sn is deposited in a multilayer SIS structure, the magnetisation loop shows no hysteresis in the loop, which can be associated with the protective effect of the multilayer, which reduces the sensitivity to flux pinning. The first penetration field was determined to be $B_{en} = 108$ mT for copper and $B_{en} = 130$ mT on sapphire. The B_{c2} for both cases was determined to be above 16 T.

Figure 3.3: (a) the x-section SEM of a triple multilayer NbTiN in SIS structure, (b) corresponding EDS depicting each layer composition, (c) the DC magnetisation loop at $T = 4.22$ K.

For NbTiN SIS multilayer as shown in Fig. 3.3, a series of samples were deposited keeping the deposition parameters constant for all layers and changing only the thickness of the layers and number of top insulating/superconducting multilayer. The best results were found to be when the underlying Nb layer was at the largest thickness of the series and independent of the number of SIS multilayer and their respective thickness.

3.2 DEPOSITION AT SIEGEN

3.2.1 System 2: NbN thin films with DC MS

The NbN system was studied in detail at University of Siegen. Initial Cu samples were coated with thin films of NbN by DCMS in order to determine the effects of the different deposition parameters on the resulting morphological, crystallographic and superconducting properties. The relationship between the achieved crystallographic phase and the resultant superconducting performances proved to be significant, with the δ -NbN (111) phase leading to higher transition temperature (T_c) values and the δ -NbN (200) phase leading to higher first entry field (B_{en}) values. Based on the results, it is evident that a higher deposition pressure and lower cathode power lead to repeatable deposition of the correct NbN phase, with a $T_c > 15.5$ K routinely achieved, as detailed in deliverable reports D15.2 and D15.3 [2,8] and as an example the difference in morphology is shown in depicted in Fig. 3.4. Unfortunately, the first entry field values achieved for these single layer NbN films do not lend themselves to use in SRF cavities, due to the low first entry field (B_{en}) values.

Figure 3.4 X-section SEM for NbN deposited at different pressure (a) low pressure and (b) high pressure.

3.2.2 Developing NbN based SIS samples on copper

In order to improve the base layer in the SIS film coatings, a series of Nb films were successfully deposited onto Cu substrates using HiPIMS. Due to the nature of the coating system, higher duty

cycles than previous investigations, in the region of 8–20%, were required. The results point to three specific deposition parameters as the most significant; the substrate temperature, substrate bias and film thickness. The observed changes in the superconducting performance are related to changes in the crystallographic structure of the Nb film, its state of stress and the resultant grain morphology in the penetration depth of the RF field. It is evident that films whose crystal structure approaches that of unstressed, bulk Nb have superior superconducting performance. Crystallographic investigations detailed the presence of a sort of transition zone during the initial few micrometres of film growth, characterised by higher stress levels and competitive growth of different Nb orientations. Films thicker than $\sim 3.5 \mu\text{m}$ present more coherent grain structures and decreased film stress, resulting in significant gains in superconducting performance. Changes to the duty cycle did not result in any significant changes to the crystallographic structure of the films. Most notably, the use of HiPIMS resulted in an 85% reduction in the number of interfacial voids.

A series of different SIS films based on the work by Gurevich [9] were also deposited. These films all utilised a Nb/AlN/NbN structure and were deposited onto electropolished Cu substrates. The coatings were concluded in a staggered fashion based on the step-wise improvements made to both the Nb and NbN layers.

Initial SIS films were deposited onto Cu using DCMS only. The films were deposited with a constant 30 nm thick AlN layer and NbN thicknesses from 80 to 150 nm. The films displayed a coherent epitaxial structure with no presence of interfacial voids between the layers. The superconducting results displayed the potential for delayed field entry, but the relatively rough DCMS Nb film resulted in some inconsistencies in the outer layers of some samples, thereby hindering interpretation of the results. These initial results were detailed in Deliverable Report D15.3 [8].

Following the completion of the HiPIMS Nb study, two sets of SIS samples were deposited, both using a HiPIMS Nb base layer and DCMS NbN layers. Two different NbN “recipes” were used for the outer shielding layer, one with high T_c and one with high B_{en} , while also investigating the role of the shielding layer thickness. The AlN layer was again maintained at 30 nm with the NbN layer varying between 100 and 250 nm. The superconducting results indicated a definite split between the two series with those deposited with the high B_{en} NbN film proving to be superior. The results also exhibited specific entry field maximums for each series, related to the shielding layer thickness, pointing to an optimum thickness as previously reported [1]. The T_c values of the NbN layers showed an increase with increasing thickness, but were similar to those of the original, single layer films. These results highlighted the importance of using high B_{en} films for the shielding layer but did not improve upon the entry field values obtained with the pure HiPIMS Nb film.

A final series of SIS samples were produced using the HiPIMS NbN recipe with the highest B_{en} while also investigating the effects of AlN and NbN film thicknesses. The AlN was set at either 8 or 30 nm, with NbN layer thicknesses between 75 and 250 nm deposited on both. The superconducting performance of these films was consistently higher than those of the previous SIS film series and surpassed that of the HiPIMS Nb film in some instances as shown in Fig. 3.5. Again, a specific

maximum in the entry field was found for a specific NbN film thickness, further pointing to its role in effectively shielding the underlying Nb film. The thickness of the NbN film which led to the highest entry field was thicker for the HiPIMS deposition compared to DCMS, indicating the cleaner state of the film, in line with previously produced theoretical models [2]. Two QPR samples were also coated with two separate SIS films to investigate the effects of the AlN layer thickness.

Figure 3.5: The normalised magnetic moments and magnetisation loop of Nb and NbN in single and multilayer structure deposited with DC and HIPIMS.

3.3 DC SUPERCONDUCTIVITY EVALUATION AT IEE

Part of the project was focused on assessing a possible utilisation of materials other than Nb (non-Nb) for SRF applications. In the DC magnetisation experiments, several sets of samples were investigated in order to compare their first flux entry field values B_{en} . The materials tested included Nb_3Sn , in single layer, double layers of Nb_3Sn/Nb and in SIS layer structures of $Nb_3Sn/AlN/Nb$. The NbTi and NbTiN materials were investigated, in single layer as well as in multilayer SIS configurations comprising 2 to 3 repetitions of the Insulator-Superconductor sequence. Utilisation of the NbN material in the SIS structures of $NbN/AlN/Nb$ has been explored as well, in several series of samples. Here both the Nb and NbN superconducting layers were deposited using the standard

DCMS method at first, then the Nb deposition method was changed to the HiPIMS, and finally both the Nb and NbN were deposited using the HiPIMS in the last series of samples.

Comparison of B_{en} values of the non-Nb films on Cu substrate is shown in Fig. 3.6. The highest B_{en} values are seen among the Nb₃Sn based double layer, SIS samples and among the NbN based SIS samples deposited via HiPIMS. The performance of the best other-than-Nb films is comparable to, but still somewhat lower than of the best Nb films.

Figure 3.6: Overview of the first flux entry fields of B_{en} for the non-Nb films on Cu substrates.

It should be noted that in the case of the multilayer films, the DC magnetisation measurements in VSM setup are not an ideal characterisation tool. The whole sample is immersed in the applied homogeneous magnetic field during the measurements and it is thus possible that the magnetic flux starts entering through the edges of the sample and in some of the sub-layers and not from the outermost layer of the multilayer structure. Local measurement methods like the third harmonic induced voltage detection or the flux penetration experiment are more suitable for multilayer films.

3.4 THE MAIN ACHIEVEMENT IN SUPERCONDUCTING THIN FILM DEVELOPMENT

The main achievement in the thin film process was that we have successfully synthesised high T_c superconducting material with T_c near the theoretical value for three different materials such as NbN, NbTiN and Nb₃Sn. A SRF cavity of these materials cannot be made from bulk, hence any implementation of such materials in a SRF cavity is through thin films and by determining the exact deposition condition it will now allow us to produce the next generation of SRF cavity which can perform at 4 K rather than 1.8 K. This will bring potentially a massive saving in running cost of future accelerators. This success has been the stepping stone to secure a further development of these films for the SRF application within a frame of the H2020 I.FAST project.

4. Study of SC thin films on QPR samples

In the previous Deliverable Reports D15.1-D15.3 [1,2,8], the impact of substrate preparation, the performance of baseline Nb coatings and the performance of several alternative superconductor layers have been presented. In the past year, the scope was shifted towards multilayer SIS samples which yielded very promising results and are presented in the following.

4.1 INVESTIGATION OF SIS MULTILAYER SAMPLES

A total of three SIS layered samples fabricated within the ARIES effort has been tested in the quadrupole resonator (QPR) so far, they are listed in Table 2. For comparison, a sample prepared at Jefferson Lab (JLab) and measured with the HZB QPR prior to ARIES is included as well.

Table 2: List of SIS samples.

	SIS films tested	Structure	Baseline	Production
JLab SIS	NbTiN – AlN – Nb(bulk)	75nm – 15 nm – bulk Nb	Yes	JLab, DCMS
ARIES 1st SIS	NbN – AlN – Nb(film)/Cu	197nm – 35 nm – 3 μm Nb	Yes	Siegen, DCMS
ARIES 2nd SIS	NbN – AlN – Nb(film)/Cu	180nm – 8 nm – 4 μm Nb	No	Siegen, HiPIMS
ARIES 3rd SIS	NbN – AlN – Nb(film)/Cu	180nm – 24 nm – 4 μm Nb	No	Siegen, HiPIMS

The first ARIES multilayer sample was prepared by DC magnetron sputtering, as described before. This technique was also used for the JLab sample. The second and third ARIES samples were prepared by HiPIMS - these samples were coated in one run without an intermediate baseline test. Besides the manufacturing technique, the main difference between the samples was the chosen thickness of the AlN insulator layer.

The surface resistance values versus temperature of all samples are plotted in Fig. 4.1. It can be seen that HiPIMS coated samples generally exhibit a better (i.e. smaller) surface resistance. As a general trend, the surface resistance is better, the thinner the insulator layer is. The likely explanation for this behaviour is that the dielectric losses in the insulator layer are proportional to the layer thickness. Hence, the measurements suggest that the impact of dielectric losses cannot be neglected in multilayer films, and making the insulator as thin as possible is mandatory for multilayered structures.

Figure 4.1: Surface resistance as a function of temperature of a series of SIS multilayer samples.

Since the purpose of the insulating layer is suppressing the proximity effect between the superconducting layers (and to avoid a Josephson junction between them), any value above ~ 1 nm for the insulator layer is acceptable - which makes the feasibility of the coating the limiting factor. Note, that this phenomenon could only be seen in true RF measurements at realistic fields, but not in the DC measurements.

The measured surface resistance curves exhibit a second feature: A non-monotonic temperature behaviour that was first discovered in the early JLab sample and then also seen in the first ARIES sample. This feature was very pronounced in the JLab sample at around 8 K and a little less pronounced and shifted to around 5 K in the ARIES sample.

The origin of the feature was unclear and it was decided to investigate further, in particular since the underlying theory did not allow for a decrease of surface resistance with temperature.

Therefore, in the second ARIES sample the insulator thickness was made as small as possible with the methods at hand (i.e. 8 nm). As a result, any peaks disappeared from the surface resistance versus temperature curve. However, since the production method was changed from DCMS to HiPIMS, it was unclear if this improvement was due to the layer thickness or the production method itself. Therefore, it was decided to produce another sample with HiPIMS and use an intermediate insulator layer thickness (24 nm) and to check if the peak re-appeared.

As can be seen in Fig. 4.1 this did not happen, no peaks were observed in the surface resistance versus temperature curve. Although the appearance of the peaks in the early samples is still not entirely understood, it is safe to say that their appearance is an indicator of extrinsic performance bias (i.e. poor film quality or trapped flux), rather than an intrinsic property of multilayer structures in general.

In order to investigate the extrinsic impact on the sample performance in more detail, the 1st ARIES sample was thermally cycled. In Figure 4.2 the effect of thermal cycling on the surface resistance is illustrated. The yellow curve shows the surface resistance after the initial cool-down, the red curves show a subsequent measurement run with intermediate warm-up to room temperature. The sample was not been touched between the runs, and was kept under vacuum in between. Nevertheless, the curves look very different: Although all curves exhibit the non-monotonic behaviour, the peaks are at different temperatures and involve different changes in surface resistances.

Figure 4.2: Thermal cycling of multilayer sample.

For the initial cool down the peak occurs at 5.5 K and 700 nΩ and is followed by a drop to 660 nΩ at 6 K. The edge of the yellow curve towards small temperatures suggests the existence of another peak which could not be fully measured due to limitations of the cryo-plant. In the second experiment the peak was shifted to a temperature of 3.5 K and smaller surface resistance of 420 nΩ and dropped below 400 nΩ towards 4.5 - 5.5 K.

The only apparent thing that could be different between the two sets of experiments was the cool-down dynamics which in SRF applications is typically closely related to the flux trapping behaviours of the SRF structure. The reason for this is that the velocity at which the temperature drops across the QPR and sample surface impacts the efficiency at which the Meissner effect of flux expulsion takes place and how much of the ambient magnetic field is trapped in the sample as residual flux. The interaction of the trapped flux with the RF field determines the residual surface resistance of the sample.

In order to test if the change of the curve was caused by magnetic flux trapping, a short warmup of all superconducting components above T_c was performed (>25 K thermocycle) in order to expose the sample to altered cool-down conditions. The resulting surface resistance vs temperature curve was almost identical up to temperatures of 3.5 K. Above 3.5 K the curves begin to differ and the local minimum of the surface resistance curves drops from 5.5 K for the pre-cycling sample to 4.5 K for the cycled sample. However, these changes are not strongly significant and only slightly beyond the statistical error bars (which are obtained from statistical averaging). The second thermocycle did not make a big difference, however, the changes in cool-down conditions might have been much less drastic than anticipated. Therefore, the source of the change of the curve and the non-monotonic behaviour is still unclear. A quantitative experiment with simultaneous measurement of the trapped flux is necessary to bring more clarity.

Promising results were also obtained during the tests of samples ARIES-2nd-SIS and ARIES-3rd-SIS: Figure 4.3 shows their respective surface resistance minus residual resistance (temperature dependent component of surface resistance) versus temperature together with a bulk Nb sample for comparison. From the plot we can extract that the temperature dependent part is growing slower than bulk Nb, which (if you consider same residual resistance) gives the advantage of about 20 nΩ compared to Nb at 4.5 K. This is expected due to the higher critical temperature of the top NbN film.

Another satisfying result was achieved with the ARIES-3rd-SIS sample, which showed low residual resistance (about 45 nΩ) and low “Q-slope” or field dependent increase of surface resistance, equivalent to bulk Nb (see Fig. 4.4). The residual resistance of the bulk Nb, presented here was about 23 nΩ. The only drawback of the film was that the maximum achieved field for NbN top layer was about 35 mT.

For further improvement, also with respect to the continuation of the work in I.FAST, the following conclusions can be made:

1. Use as thin as possible insulator layers.
2. HiPIMS works better.

In the future the following topics should be addressed:

- A. The limitation of the maximum field needs to be studied.
- B. Further decrease residual resistance.

Figure 4.3: Temperature-dependant component of surface resistance with subtracted residual resistance.

Figure 4.4: R_s vs field for the HiPIMS made samples in comparison with a bulk Nb sample.

4.2 QPR TEST OF LASER TREATED NB THIN FILMS

One of the copper based QPR samples (B5) has been deposited with a 3- μm thick Nb film at STFC, the results has been reported in D15.3 [8]. After the SRF testing this sample at HZB, the sample was sent to RTU for laser treatment (as described in Section 5.3). Figure 4.5 shows the sample before and after laser treatment.

Figure 4.5: The QPR sample (a) before and (b) after irradiation by Nd:YAG laser at intensity $I = 75 \text{ MW/cm}^2$.

The results of the RF test with the QPR are presented in Fig. 4.6. The baseline RF test of the sample prior to the laser polishing procedure exhibited a limited maximum field and several significant jumps in surface resistance vs peak field space, the most likely explanation being the “Q-switch” effect due to an imperfect film which allows for hysteretic flux trapping, fed by the applied RF field. The laser polishing was intended to reduce the film roughness, defects and delamination and since it was

Figure 4.6: Results of the RF test with the QPR at HZB, for the laser polished Nb thin film. Sample temperature during the RF test: (a) 2.5 K, and (b) 4.5 K.

performed on a QPR sample, it was possible to test the impact of the procedure for the first time in real RF conditions. From the results we can conclude that after laser polishing we obtained an increased residual resistance, but managed to make the curve (e.g. field dependent component) “smoother”. For example, at around 20 mT and 4.5 K the surface resistance was even lower than the baseline value. The maximum field was also shifted slightly to the higher values (from 25 to 27 mT). But this result might be explicable by a different field configuration on the sample surface due to samples rotation between the tests: prior and post polishing.

In an attempt to understand the RF results better, the surface of the laser polished sample was investigated with a laser scanning microscope. The full scan is depicted in Fig 4.7. Several major defects were observed. For example, the crater labelled “1” is the result of either an overpowered laser pulse or high radiation energy absorption of the surface in that region. That spot is shown in greater detail in Figure 4.8. In that region the defect is so deep that the underlying Cu substrate is exposed to the RF field. Such defects can easily make a significant contribution to the residual surface resistance. Hence, an explanation for the seeming performance drop might be that it was caused by defects, which overshadow any improvement that might have been achieved in the remainder of the surface area. We can conclude that the laser polishing needs to be optimized, especially for thin films. The film surface should be homogeneous without larger defects that create the risk of increased absorption of the laser power which results in a major defect later.

Figure 4.7: Result of the sample scan: 1- Major defect near the edge, 2 - Minor craters in high field region, 3 - laser traces near the edge, 4 - a “group of craters”.

Figure 4.8: Defect 1 - Surface profile of major defect near the edge.

Figure 4.9 shows a confocal laser scanning image of the sample surface that reveals in great detail the traces from the mechanical milling of the copper sample surface (concentric lines) and superimposed the traces the traveling laser beam (smaller parallel features). These features extend over the entire surface in a similar manner. Figure 4.9 also reveals a different type defect feature resulting from the laser treatment: a number of equidistant minor craters along the azimuth. The origin of these features is unknown, but it is clear that additional optimization of the procedure is needed.

4.3 SUMMARY FOR STUDYING THE SC THIN FILMS ON QPR SAMPLES

One of the main scopes of the ARIES WP15 has been successfully achieved with these measurements: A processing chain for SRF thin film samples has been established, where every partner contributes manufacturing steps according to their laboratories' expertise. The lessons learned from the preparation, materials- and DC characterisation of the films have been applied to QPR samples which were as the final step RF-tested in the quadrupole resonator. The RF tests reveal important information that cannot be obtained by other means, such as, for example, the RF surface resistance of the sample. Also, due to the considerable RF-active area of a QPR sample, the QPR measurements reveal information about the upscaling of the coating procedure which will eventually have to be extended to curved surfaces of cavities.

A direct result of the QPR measurements is the insight that the insulating layer in SIS samples needs to be made as small as possible in order to avoid dielectric losses.

Figure 4.9. Defect 2 - minor craters in high field region. The sample shows clear traces from the mechanical milling procedure which survived the subsequent chemistry as well as the laser polishing step. The traces of the laser polishing can be seen as horizontal lines which reveal the path of the laser across the sample surface.

Another outcome was the insight, that the non-monotonic features sometimes observed in surface resistance versus temperature samples were caused by poor film quality rather than unknown physical effects, and can therefore be used as a criterion for a poor film in the future.

5. Exploration of new technologies for SRF

The H2020 ARIES collaboration enables institutions and researchers, who have not been related to particle accelerators in the past, to contribute their expertise and experience to the accelerator community. Thus, WP15 involves three institutions: Siegen University with their expertise in thin film deposition and characterisation, IEE from Bratislava with experience and experimental capability in superconductors and evaluating their properties, and RTU from Riga with expertise in laser surface engineering and characterisation. Within the duration of ARIES, these three institutions have become an integrated part of the TF SRF community. A number of new ideas were explored in WP15 for applying for SC TF characterisation and treatments. The main results are described in this Section.

5.1 LASER POLISHING OF COPPER SUBSTRATE

Metal surface polishing with a laser radiation is widely used in R&D and industry [25,26]. The laser radiation polishing of copper surface has been explored for the possibility of reducing the surface roughness of Cu substrate used for the following superconducting film deposition. The polishing of Cu substrate before deposition of Nb is necessary for improving mechanical, thermal and magnetic properties of Nb thin film on Cu structure of the RF cavity.

The laser radiation was carried out in Riga Technical University on a sample C18 cleaned by INFN. The sample was irradiated by an NdYAG laser with a wavelength of 532 nm, an intensity of 1.2 GW/cm², beam diameter of 3 mm and laser pulse duration of 4 ns in a ‘point-to-point’ regime. Optical images of C18 sample before and after laser polishing are shown in Fig. 5.1.

From Fig. 5.1(a) one can see that Cu substrate is polycrystalline with different crystal orientations and wide range of crystal size distribution (up to 20 μm). The surface after laser irradiation is shown in Fig. 5.1(b). A laser ablation of small crystals took place because the small crystals on the surface (with a size less than thermal diffusion length) were heated up to the melting temperature much quicker than the bigger crystals. As a result, the bigger crystals remain on the irradiated surface, leading to a higher roughness.

This result demonstrates that the laser polishing of copper:

- is not as simple as on other metals due to two parameters: its high and not uniform photon reflectivity as well as high thermal conductivity [27];
- requires more careful choice of the copper material (for example: large grain copper);
- requires more R&D in future.

Figure 5.1: Optical microscope images of C18 sample: (a) Non-irradiated; (b) Laser polished (irradiated by 10 pulses of Nd:YAG laser).

5.2 POST DEPOSITION LASER TREATMENT OF Nb FILMS

5.2.1 Small samples

An **adhesion** of a 3- μm thick Nb thin film to a bulk (2-mm thick) Cu substrate as well as a size of Nb crystal grains were studied depending on laser intensity and dose. The Nb/Cu structures obtained by magnetron sputtering with a deposition temperature of 500 and 700 °C were irradiated by a pulsed Nd:YAG laser.

Figure 5.2. Optical microscope images of Nb/Cu structure: (a) before irradiation and (b) after the irradiation by laser with $I = 253 \text{ MW/cm}^2$. Yellow arrows show delaminated Nb from Cu

The film adhesion/delamination strength was investigated by a scratching method using a conical diamond indenter with an applied force increasing from 10 mN to 3.0 N. Characterization of the surface structure was performed before and after the irradiation using an optical microscope, AFM,

SEM and XRD. Comparing with the non-irradiated area, the critical delamination force for laser treated films increased by 36% (see Fig. 5.2).

A decrease of average **roughness** of Nb layer by an order of magnitude was observed after the laser irradiation (see field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) images in Fig. 5.3). The improvement of the structure adhesion was explained by the diffusion of Nb atoms into Cu through dislocations.

The increase of Nb **crystallite size** from 20 to 35 nm was calculated using XRD data. All experiments were carried out in Ar atmosphere, room temperature, and atmospheric pressure.

Figure 5.3: FESEM images of Nb/Cu sample (a) before the irradiation and (b) after the irradiation by Nd:YAG laser with intensities $I = 253 \text{ MW/cm}^2$.

Magnetic flux penetration into the superconducting Nb films deposited on Cu substrate has been investigated by means of magnetisation measurements at IEE. Using a commercial Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) set-up, virgin DC magnetization curves and magnetization loops were measured on small measurement samples of approximately $2 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$. The main characteristic determined from the magnetization curves was the first flux entry field B_{en} , determined as the applied field at which the magnetic flux starts entering the sample's volume. Figure 5.4 shows the result for small pieces cut from Samples L16 and L20 and either untreated or laser treated with 4 different doses in the range between 140 and 350 J/cm^2 .

Figure 5.4: The first magnetic flux entry field H_{en} as a function of the laser dose (D) used for irradiation of the L16 series (triangles) and L20 series (circles) samples.

It has been demonstrated that:

1. The adhesion of Nb film can be improved: the critical delamination force for irradiated Nb/Cu structure is increased after the laser dose by maximally 36%.
2. The laser irradiation of Nb/Cu structure leads to a decrease of average surface roughness from 7.6 to 0.5 nm, according to AFM results.
3. The crystalline size in the Nb layer is increased by 20% after the irradiation of the structure by Nd:YAG laser at the intensity $I = 200 \text{ MW/cm}^2$.
4. The first magnetic flux entry field B_{en} initially increases with the laser energy dose, reaches a maximum and then decreases. For both samples L16 and L20 the first magnetic flux entry field B_{en} of laser treated samples with $D = 150 \text{ J/cm}^2$ is significantly higher than for the untreated samples.

5.2.2 QPR sample treatment and testing

These results were applied to the QPR sample. It was found that laser parameters for the Nd:YAG laser found on the small samples do not provide the same results on QPR samples (too high intensity). The trial laser treatment was performed with a faulty QPR-B1, demonstrating that the required laser intensity that provides a Nb surface similar to ones studied with small samples should be much lower: $I = 75 \text{ MW/cm}^2$. After that this procedure was applied to the QPR samples. The results of the RF text are reported in Section 4.2.

5.3 EXPLORING EVALUATION OF SUPERCONDUCTING FILMS WITH PHOTO- AND THERMOSTIMULATED EXOELECTRON EMISSION SPECTRA AT RTU

Another study performed at RTU aimed to explore the possibility of using photo- and thermostimulated exoelectron emission to superconducting thin film evaluation. The analysis of results was performed on samples obtained from the first set of 14 samples of Nb films, deposited by ARIES project partners on the Cu substrates, which were initially pre-processed by different methods. No relationships found between parameters of photo- and thermostimulated exoelectron emission spectra and Cu substrate preparation method. No correlation was found between photo- and thermostimulated exoelectron emission and surface roughness of Cu substrate and deposited Nb layers, as well as photo- and thermostimulated exoelectron emission and magnetic characteristic of the Nb films. The main conclusion was that this method is not suitable in present stay for characterising superconducting thin films.

5.4 MAGNETIC FIELD PENETRATION MEASUREMENTS

There are various methods of evaluating the properties of superconductors, among them there are residual-resistivity ratio (RRR), magnetisation measurements in DC magnetic field (such as VSM and SQUID), AC magnetisation (AC magnetic susceptibility, 3rd harmonic). Each method has its advantages and provides specific information related to properties of superconductors. However, the

correlation between the measured characteristic and behaviour of this superconductor at the RF condition at the walls of an RF cavity is still not fully understood.

The RF losses in an RF cavity coated with superconducting TF will increase as soon as the magnetic field reaches the copper substrate. Full magnetic field penetration method allows to study the superconducting TF efficiency as the magnetic screen. The earlier realisations of this method were reported in Ref. [13]. A new system shown in Figure 5.5 has been built, tested and is fully operational at STFC from October 2020.

Figure 5.5: (a) Schematic layout and (b) operational facility for magnetic field penetration measurements.

The main features of this method are the following:

- This method is developed for magnetic field penetration measurements with planar samples (most common geometry for research).
- A C-shaped dipole magnet applies a DC magnetic field over a 2mm gap to ensure a homogeneous field without edge effects.
- The magnetic field is applied from one side of the sample and parallel to the sample surface (similar to an SRF cavity).
- The applied and penetrating fields are measured by Hall probe sensors.
- The method is suitable for single and multilayer (SIS) samples.

This facility is built with a cryogen-free cryostat, cooled with a Sumitomo RDK-408D2 cold head.

The operation parameters are the following:

- Sample temperature: $2.6 \text{ K} < T < 10 \text{ K}$,
- Applied magnetic field $B = 0 - 600 \text{ mT}$ for $I = 0 - 8 \text{ A}$,
- Sample size between $35 \text{ mm} \times 35 \text{ mm}$ and $52 \text{ mm} \times 52 \text{ mm}$.

5.5 SUMMARY FOR EXPLORATION OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES FOR SRF

The ARIES WP15 provides a great opportunity for exploring four technologies, which have not been used in the past for the R&D related to the SRF cavities. Two of them were found to be practical for SRF applications:

Based on the reported experimental work, laser treatment of Nb films could be an additional tool for improving performance of both the bulk Nb and Nb thin film coated cavities.

The magnetic field penetration method has already attracted the attention of researchers in the field. In total, about 20 samples have already been characterised and more samples are scheduled to be studied in near future.

6. Conclusions and future plans

The ARIES WP15 team made significant progress with the production of superconducting thin film coatings on copper samples.

- It highlighted the importance of copper substrate surface preparation and polishing. At present, EP and SUBU5 have shown the best results for Nb film deposited after these polishing. These results were further developed and applied to QPR samples.
- Thin film development consisted of 3 systems different from commonly used Nb: System 1 (Nb₃Sn), System 2 (NbN), System 3 (NbTiN), then these system have been applied to SIS structures (NbN:AlN:Nb, as well as Nb₃Sn:AlN:Nb and NbTiN:AlN:Nb). Each system has been deposited and characterised with surface characterisation instruments and DC magnetometry. Furthermore, the SIS structures (Nb₃Sn:AlN:Nb₃Sn:AlN:Nb) and SS structures (Nb₃Sn:Nb, NbTiN:NbTiN, NbTi:Nb) have been investigated. Finally, a few of these systems have been applied for QPR coating.
- The results obtained with the QPR measurements show the correlation between the performance of superconducting thin films under RF conditions and all other characterisations and tests obtained on small samples such as: thin film composition, structure, morphology, magnetisation measurement, etc. Therefore, further development could continue without the need to coat a more expensive real cavity, i.e. at lower cost and higher sample turnout rate.
- Four technologies, which have not been used in the past for the R&D related to the SRF cavities, have been explored. Two of them were found to be practical for SRF applications: a laser treatment of Nb films and magnetic field penetration measurements.
- Beyond the original scope of WP15 it was found that thickness and thermal properties of the insulator layer in an SIS composite superconductor play an important role for its RF performance. This result has not been predicted by theory and will have to be taken into consideration in future applications of SIS structures

In general, the ARIES WP15 team achieved all of its goals, the Milestones and Deliverables have been successfully completed. The team progressed with better understanding of an impact of the Cu substrate polishing and impact of various polishing techniques on a quality of superconducting films. The SC film deposition process has been developed for producing various superconducting thin films characterisation. The collaboration effort results in better understanding of a correlation between substrate preparation, deposition process, thin film characteristic, the DC and AC SC evaluation results and the TF behaviour at the RF conditions.

The knowledge and experience obtained by WP partners in copper substrate preparation and deposition of non-Nb TF materials with higher T_c are enabling progressing to the next stage: developing a real cavity prototype coated with non-Nb superconducting TF and SIS structures. The potential benefit of this should be increasing of Q_0 and E characteristics, a possibility of operation for SRF cavities at 4 K instead of 1.8 K leading to reducing the initial and operation costs the RF systems. In the follow-up project within H2020 I.FAST WP9, all this will be initially applied to 6 and 3 GHz copper cavities for developing a 3D coating technology, then it should be demonstrated with a 1.3 GHz copper cavity which should be deposited with non-Nb SC TF (including SIS structures) and fully tested with a RF power.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AFM	Atomic Force Microscope

CEA	Saclay Nuclear Research Centre - Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique
CERN	European Council for Nuclear Research
DCMS	Direct current magnetron sputtering
EDS	Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometry
EP	Electropolishing
HiPIMS	High power impulse magnetron sputtering
HZB	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
IEE	Institute of Electrical Engineering Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava
INFN-LNL	Italian Institute of Nuclear Physics - Legnaro National Laboratories
OFE	Oxygen Free Electronic copper
OFHC	Oxygen-Free High thermal Conductivity copper
PPMS	Physical Property Measurement System
QPR	Quadrupole Resonator
QWR	Quarter Wave Resonator
RF	Radio Frequency
RTU	Riga Technical University
SC	Superconductivity
SIS	Superconductor-Insulator- Superconductor
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
SRF	Superconducting Radio Frequency
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council - Daresbury Laboratory
SUBU	Chemical Polishing of Cu with a solution of Sulphamic Acid and Butanol
T _c	Critical temperature of superconducting transition (thermodynamic)

TF	Thin films
USI	University of Siegen
VSM	Vibrating Sample Magnetometer
XRD	X-Ray Diffraction